

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Without mass, no electric charge

Short communication

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

Ilija Barukčić

Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2024; Volume: 19; Issue: 11; pp. 5–16.

✉ Received: June 4, 2023

✓ Accepted: June 7, 2023

📅 Published: June 7, 2023

📖 [Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt](#)

📄 [ISSN: 1863-9542](#)

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8012301](#)

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid](#) [Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Mass and electric charge appear to us as two sides of the same coin. However, what is electric charge anyway?

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The relationship between mass and electric charge was considered from the point of view of classical logic.

RESULTS:

We have to accept the relationship: without mass, no charge. It should also be noted that charge is a sufficient condition of mass too. In other words, if electric charge, then mass.

CONCLUSION:

It is possible to separate mass and charge.

Keywords:

Masse; Elektric charge; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

☉ Reviewer 1: None/Author.

☉ Reviewer 2: None.

☉ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Electric charge as a physical property of matter can be positive or negative (classical electrodynamics). The two types of electric charge are treated as equal but opposite. Unlike charges are attracting each other, while like charges repel each other. Furthermore, matter or mass with an absence of net charge is referred to as neutral. However, why is electric charge given, why does it exist, where does electric charge originate from? An electric field, also called an electrical field or an electrostatic field, is surrounded by any object that has charge and radiates outward from a charged object in all directions? What happens with the energy and the charge itself of such an object? Furthermore, what is the relationship between electric charge and an electromagnetic field? Can electric charge exist without an electromagnetic field? Can an electromagnetic field exist without charge? In point of fact, what was there first, the hen or the egg, the electric charge or the electromagnetic field or both or none? Does the net charge of the universe equal zero?

As a result of experiments and other forms of scientific inquiry based on premises, the view that accommodations are superior to predictions in the assessment of scientific theories about electric charge might be common. Especially, the question of the nature of the relationship between mass and charge is so controversial that no brief account of it will satisfy all those with a stake in the debates between mass-ists and charge-ists. Charge is mass, mass is charge or both or none or what? Thus far, it is misleading to think that there is a straightforward and clear-cut choice between a mass and a charge. Therefore and independent of being as an author selectively realist or non-realist about various topics, even a “speculative mode of cognition” (i.e. Hegel’s dialectics) might ask questions about fundamental relationships such as between mass and charge in unique ways. Mass and charge are one of the most central subjects in physics and may be also one of the largest. However, the distinctions between mass and charge in today’s physics, i.e. the electrodynamics of charged particles, concentrate mainly around a physical quantity relating the mass (quantity of matter (m)) and the quantity of electric charge (Q) of a given mass (mass-to-charge ratio (m/Q)).

Historically, the first mass-to-charge ratio of the electron was first measured by J. J. Thomson (see [Thomson, 1897](#)) in 1897. In 1898, Wilhelm Carl Werner Otto Fritz Franz Wien (1864–1928) developed a device (see [Wien, 1898](#)) consisting of perpendicular electric and magnetic fields (Wien filter) which can be used as a velocity filter for charged particles. In what follows, we will concentrate mainly on the logical content of the relationship between mass and charge. Finally, and most generally, can we describe the relationship between mass and charge as a natural process that involves something like a contradictory process between opposing sides that are opposed to one another without generating only approximate truths? In point of fact, are charge and mass only two distinct properties of matter? We know that it is possible for a particle to have a charge without having mass (such as a photon) and vice versa. It is possible to have mass without having charge (such as a neutron). However, these examples do not answer the question, how are mass and charge ultimately related, what is the logical relation and tie between charge and mass?

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The Standard Model of particle physics describes to some extent the weak, the electromagnetic and the strong interactions between leptons and quarks, which are equally the basic particles of the Standard Model (Cottingham and Greenwood, 2007). However, a massive drawback of the standard model is that it excludes from consideration the gravitational field. In general, it is believed to be true of all interactions that they preserve electric charge. However, is there and what kind of relationship could there be between mass and charge? One aspect of the relationship between mass and electric charge is illustrated with the following table (see table 1) while relying on the Standard Model of particle physics.

2.1.1. Without mass, no electric charge

Table 1. Without mass, no electric charge

		Electric charge		
		YES	NO	
Mass	YES	Proton Electron W+ Boson W- Boson Muon ...	Neutron Neutrinos Z0-Boson Higgs-Boson ...	Invariant mass is not zero
	NO	0	Photon Gluon Graviton ...	Invariant mass is zero
		Charge	No charge	Unity

Invariant mass is a necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) of electric charge.

2.1.2. If electric charge, then mass

Another aspect of the relationship between mass and electric charge follows with logical necessity and is illustrated by the following table (see table 2) while again relying on the Standard Model of particle physics.

Table 2. If electric charge, then mass

		Mass		
		YES	NO	
Electric charge	YES	Proton Electron W+ Boson W- Boson Muon ...	0	Electric charge
	NO	Neutron Neutrinos Z0-Boson Higgs-Boson ...	Photon Gluon Graviton ...	No electric charge

Invariant mass No invariant mass Unity

Electric charge is a sufficient condition (*conditio per quam*) of invariant mass.

3. Results

3.1. Theorem: Without mass, no electric charge

Theorem 1 (Without mass, no electric charge). *In general, we have reason to believe that the relationship **without** mass, **no** electric charge.*

Proof by direct proof. In a rough overview of the Standard Model of particle physics (Cottingham and Greenwood, 2007), it was impossible to identify one single particle (see table 1), which does possess electric charge, but does not possess mass. We may therefore assume for the moment and of course only provisionally as proven that the relation **without** mass, **no** electric charge is valid.

□

3.2. Theorem: If electric charge, then mass

Theorem 2 (If electric charge, then mass). *In general, we have reason to believe that the relationship **if** electric charge, **then** mass is valid.*

Proof by direct proof. Again, in a superficial overview of the Standard Model of particle physics (Cottingham and Greenwood, 2007), it was impossible to identify one single particle (see table 2), which does possess electric charge, but does not possess mass. Therefore, we are authorized to assume as provisionally proven that the relation **if** electric charge, **then** mass is given.

□

4. Discussion

However, theorem 1 and theorem 2 have various consequences as a result. Foremost, may we take these insights so strictly. Energy itself, in terms of general relativity (Einstein, 1916) represented by the stress-energy tensor of matter, can manifest itself in various forms. Energy can exist as an electromagnetic field, which possess no invariant mass (see table 3).

Table 3. Einstein field equations and electric charge

		Invariant mass		
		YES	NO	
Energy	YES	1	Electro-magnetic field	Stress-energy tensor
	NO	0	1	Gravitation

Curvature No curvature Ricci tensor

In other words, based on Einstein's general relativity, we are inclined to consider conditions where the relationship **without** energy, **no** invariant mass is given. In the same regard, we have to consider the fact, that theorem **without** mass, **no** electric charge (see table 1) is true. In the following, we consider theorem 7: $((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t) = +1$ of the publication Single and compound conditions ¹, Version 2 or in spoken language: $((\text{energy} \leftarrow \text{mass}) \wedge (\text{mass} \leftarrow \text{electric charge})) \rightarrow (\text{energy} \leftarrow \text{electric charge}) = +1$ while \wedge denotes logical operator: conjugation and \leftarrow denotes logical relationship necessary condition. Expressed in the everyday language. If it is true that (**without** energy, **no** mass) and (**without** mass, **no** electric charge), then it is equally (Einstein, 1935) true that (**without** energy, **no** electric charge). In other words, electric charge is a certain or special kind of energy. However, in case that it is allowed to consider electric charge as a special form of energy, access to this form of energy by experiments, should theoretically be possible. In point of fact, what happens with the relationship between mass and charge especially under conditions at extremely low cryogenic temperatures (i. e. condensed matter physics) or under conditions of heating a neutral gas or subjecting it to a strong electromagnetic field (sun, stars, plasma physics). In other words, reversing

¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>, p. 24.

the configuration of matter (Reverse Engineering Of Matter) or controlling the separation of mass and charge and the separate storage of mass and charge appears theoretically to be within reach. For the time to come, reverse engineering of matter will enable a technical mass production of antimatter with all the thinkable consequences.

Table 4. Industrial mass production of antimatter

Like many other possibilities, this technology appears to be only be a matter of time. However, such a technology might turn out to be a massive, and potentially very dangerous intervention of humans into the act of the creation or of the beginning of this world.

5. Conclusion

What will come, will come. Today, we have a good theoretical reason for the following belief.

‘Mass and charge can be separated and can be stored separately.’

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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Associated Data

None.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

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